

www.bjisrd.com

SHORT-TERM MODELS OF ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF REGIONS

Burkhanov Aktam Usmanovich

Doctor of Economical Sciences (DSc), professor

International School of Finance and Technology, Tashkent, Uzbekistan

E-mail: aktam.b@isft.uz

Abstract. In this article, the scientific-theoretical aspects of socio-economic development of regions are studied and their short-term models are presented. Also, socio-economic development indices of the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2023 were analyzed and relevant conclusions were drawn from the analysis.

Key words: model, socio-economic development, index, sub-index, period, regions.

1. Introduction

In the world, scientific studies are being carried out on regional location of industry, determining the factors influencing the priority development of new promising branches of industry, in the study of the process of industrial development based on the development of industry in regions, the establishment of innovation centers, and the creation of clusters. In particular, canoe clusters are important in terms of various aspects of general behavior, geographic location, sources of innovation, common suppliers and production factors, the interdependence of industrial and regional development, optimization of interregional economic relations, and the use of the cluster system in establishing mutually beneficial activities of various economic entities. scientific research works are being carried out.

In the context of socio-economic reforms [1] implemented in Uzbekistan in recent years, issues of regional economic policy improvement and implementation of the cluster mechanism occupy an important place. Based on the organization of industrial clusters in the regions, it is possible to further improve the added value chain, optimize costs, ensure product competitiveness, and increase people's living standards and incomes as a result of achieving synergy effects.

2. Analysis of literature on the topic

The issues of scientific study of socio-economic development of regions and their elimination have always been in the focus of attention of economists and scientists. In particular, foreign economists A. Venables, H. Glenn [5], P. Krugman, B. Robert [2], M. Fujita [3], B. Shaun have discussed the theoretical and practical aspects of this issue, in particular, issues of increasing regional competitiveness. , M. Enright [4] and others have contributed greatly.

In Uzbekistan, socio-economic development of regions and its econometric modeling have been the field of scientific interest of economists in this regard. In particular, issues such as modeling of socio-economic development of regions, complex development of regions, improvement of the methodological bases of using the economic potential of the country's regions were discussed by Uzbek economists S.S. Gulomov [6], T.M. Akhmedov [9], A.M. Sodikov [7], A.M. Kadirov, Sh.H. Nazarov, B. Rozmetov [8], Sh.B.Imomov [10], P.Z. Khashimov, F.T. Egamberdiev, A.A. Qayumov [11], A.J.Siddikov [12],

I.O.Yakubov [13] and others have a wide place in scientific research.

However, most of the above-mentioned scientific researches are directly devoted to the issues of general socio-economic development of the regions, and the short-term models of the regions have not been studied. The lack of attention to the problem studied in this article and the fact that it has a controversial description require a new scientific approach to the problem.

3. Analysis and results

It is known that the theory of socio-economic development cycles of regions in science is based on the approach of economic subjects' expectations of the evolutionary development of the economy. Well-known foreign scientists focused on the issues of theoretical substantiation of the role of expectations in the cyclical development of economic systems, using the models of R. Lucas, A. Pigou, S. Fisher, C. Nelson and other scientists. At the same time, the empirical grounding of these theoretical and methodological concepts allows us to look at them from a new practical perspective. In addition, it allows determining the degree of influence of certain parameters that determine the expectations of economic agents on the nature of phase changes in cyclical development.

The development of any economic system predetermines the corresponding models of behavior, the phases of the development of economic subjects are close to the characteristics of the evolutionary development of the classical periods (crisis, depression, recovery, rise). At the same time, socio-economic development is the result of a change in a group of indicators that describe real, financial and cultural-institutional parameters.

The following indexes (factors) are included in the construction of short-term models of socio-economic development of regions:

1. Urban development change index.
2. Human capital index
3. Production index
4. Social welfare index
5. Economic activity index
6. Research potential index
7. Capital change index
8. Socio-ecological well-being index
9. Internationalized global economy index.

Thus, the creation of a secondary statistical database of indicators affecting the socio-economic and cyclical development trends of the regions (based on the data on the website of the State Statistics Agency under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan) will confirm the reliability of the concept of rapid development cycles or, on the contrary, a set of data necessary for conducting empirical research. made it possible to create as the main methodological tool used in the development of periodic economic development forecasting functions.

All factors selected to create composite indices are presented in the form of chain growth rates at comparable prices. This is necessary to maintain the same size for all components, because otherwise it will be impossible to calculate cumulative indices. Thus, 33 sub-indices were created based on 9 indicators, and statistical data were collected on 14 administrative regions in 2020-2023. At the same time, among the factors that have a short-term effect on the model of the behavior of economic agents, there are factors that fully correspond to the existing theoretical and methodological approaches of modeling, the so-called Kitchin cycles. At the same time, the manifestation of signs of rapid development of the factors characterizing the institutional and cultural potential of the system is a very unexpected result, and the identified phenomenon undoubtedly requires appropriate explanation and justification.

As for the factors included in the group of conditional indicators involved in the calculation and

evaluation of long-term periods of advanced development, everything here fully corresponds to the paradigm of the long-wave theory. According to it, the main factor of cyclical development is the unevenness of innovative activity in the economy, which forms changes in technological structures. Or, according to Y. Schumpeter's theory, "... the main driving force of long-term fluctuations in the capitalist economy is the wave dynamics of technical and technological innovations."

It is worth noting that the nature of the rapid development, at first glance, was not manifested by such obvious factors as oil price indices (in terms of their rapid development). The results of cross-correlation analysis showed the adapted nature of their development dynamics compared to the reference series.

Determining the set of factors involved in the development of the model of rapid development cycles made it possible to move to the next stages of calculations of sub-indices that determine the economic value of economic entities aimed at evaluating the total values of grouped indicators.

In accordance with the methodological approaches presented above, the process of evaluating the values of composite indices, which include groups of factors with delayed variables, consisted of the following sequence of actions:

1. Determine the ratio of the calculated indicators to the previous year and turn them into a coefficient (index).

2. Calculation of the average arithmetic index between the regions in the studied period.

3. Identifying and summarizing above-average and below-average areas in each period.

For this, the socio-economic indicators of the regions of our country for the years 2020-2023 were obtained, the results of the calculation of short-term periods are presented in Table 1 below.

Table 1 presents the final calculations of the obtained values of the socio-economic development sub-indices of the regions.

Table 1

Deviation of the integrated indexes of socio-economic development of the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020 from the (conditional) threshold value

Areas	I_{common}	Deviation from the limit value
Republic of Karakalpakstan	0,792376843	-0,601493157
Andijan region	1,001334046	-0,392535954
Bukhara region	0,746490742	-0,647379258
Jizzakh region	1,568823354	0,174953354
Kashkadarya region	0,817930131	-0,575939869
Navoi region	1,060135072	-0,333734928
Namangan region	5,363921921	3,970051921
Samarkand region	1,309330498	-0,084539502
Surkhandarya region	0,926560203	-0,467309797
Syrdarya region	1,501892478	0,108022478
Tashkent region	1,219825227	-0,174044773
Fergana region	1,280506564	-0,113363436
Khorezm region	0,884120274	-0,509749726
Tashkent city	1,040950014	-0,352919986

At the same time, in the context of the applied research methodology, it includes the analysis of the laws of cyclic development and the implementation of diagnostics. Its essence is to study the influence of individual sub-indices on the development direction of the composite index of advanced development. In

a generalized form, the results of this type of analysis for the studied time period are presented in Table 1 and Table 2.

The highest level of impact on the dynamics of the advanced development index, which forms the general direction of the developed short-term period, is characteristic of sub-indexes - Human capital index, - Capital change index, - Social welfare index, as well as - Economic activity index. These indices to a large extent form the ideas of business entities about the stability of the development of the market situation, as well as determine the expectations regarding the economic and investment activity of business entities in the near future, which is fully consistent with the traditional theories of contraction.

It is interesting that factors related to the institutional category (sub-indices) have a significant impact on the direction of short-term cycles of accelerated development. This phenomenon, of course, requires additional studies and comments, because it is traditionally believed that short-term cyclical fluctuations are dominated by market factors (changes in interest rates, monetary policy adjustments, etc.). The influence of factors at the institutional level determines the medium and long-term perspectives in the field of changing socio-economic structures.

At the same time, the use of conceptual approaches to understanding the objects studied in our model through the prism of adaptive assumptions of economic subjects allows us to look at the cyclical development of the economy with a certain delay. And this, in turn, creates an important predictive potential of the advanced development cycles model.

In addition, the tools included in the methodological apparatus for the study of advanced development cycles, which provide the implementation of factor analysis, allow to determine the "contribution" of each subindex to the trajectory of cyclical fluctuations.

Table 2

Threshold values of socio-economic development of regions

Year	I_1 - Urban development change index	I_2 - Human capital index	I_3 - Production index	I_4 - Social welfare index	I_5 - Economic activity index	I_6 - Research capacity index	I_7 - Capital change index	I_8 - Socio-ecological well-being index	I_9 - Internati onalized global econom y index
2020	1,018	1,06	1,045	1,046	1,024	1,117	1,63	1,001	0,63
2021	1,016	1,047	1,209	1,079	1,06	1,34	1,603	1,59	1,58
2022	1,018	1,124	0,932	1,084	1,085	1,38	1,33	1,35	2,93
2023	1,019	1,07	1,0	1,0	0,918	1	0,97	1,03	1,22

According to the directions presented in Figure 1, which describe individual "elements" of expectations of economic entities based on changes in a certain sub-index, some differences in their development trends and directions can be observed.

Figure 1. Index of urban development

It is worth noting that the lack of clear cyclicity in development trends (current sinusoidal type of change) during the study period is observed only in the index of capital change (I_7) and the index of urban development (I_1). All other sub-indices that determine the values of the cumulative index of advanced development show the cyclic nature of their directions.

Figure 2. Human capital index

For example, from a scientific and educational point of view, the identified model of the cyclical development of the human capital index is very interesting. Until 1997, the values of the considered indicator showed negative values, which indicated negative opinions on the current and future models of the effectiveness of adapting developing human capital to market needs. However, starting from 2021, the trend revived until 2023. This period was characterized by the rapid development of the country's economy, which was reflected in the increase in the demand for labor.

Thus, it can be noted that a number of factors influence the composite index of advanced development, which reflects the state of current expectations of economic entities regarding future economic development. Furthermore, such influence may have multidirectional trends depending on their institutional and/or market orientation.

As part of the final stage of modeling socio-economic development cycles for the period from 2020 to 2023, the trends in the cumulative index of advanced development are calculated as the sum of the product of the absolute values of the sub-indices and their coefficients. The results of the structured model evaluating the dynamics of expectations of economic agents explain cyclical fluctuations in economic

activity.

An important aspect of the obtained results is that here the cyclical fluctuations have a short-term character, since the lag values of the studied factors are on average 1-2 years. In this regard, the forecast for further fluctuations in economic conditions is also limited to 1-2 years.

A methodologically important point is that the current algorithm for diagnosing cyclical fluctuations allows to accurately determine the up and down phases of cycles, regardless of whether they "enter" the positive or negative zone of advanced development indices.

4. Conclusion

In this article, short-term models of socio-economic development of regions are presented, and socio-economic development indices of the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020-2023 are analyzed. Accordingly, we can see that the deviation was positive in Namangan and Syrdarya regions in 2020, and a positive situation was observed in Andijan, Samarkand, Syrdarya, Fergana and Khorezm regions in 2021.

According to the results of the analysis of statistical data in 2023, a positive situation was observed in Jizzakh, Kashkadarya, Navoi, Samarkand, Khorezm regions and Tashkent city.

References:

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг “2022 — 2026 йилларга мўлжалланган Янги Ўзбекистоннинг Тараққиёт стратегияси тўғрисида”ги Фармони, 28.01.2022 йилдаги ПФ-60-сон. <https://lex.uz/docs/5841063>
2. Roberts B. National and regional corporate spatial structure / B. Roberts, A. Murray // *The Annals of Regional Science*. 2002. Vol. 36.;
3. Fujita -M., Krugman P., Venables A.J. *The Spatial Economy: Cities, Regions and International Trade*. - The MIT Press, 2001. P. 384.
4. Enright M. *The Geographical Scope of Competitive Advantage // Stuck in the Region? Changing scales for regional identity / Ed. By E. Dirven, J. Grocnewegen and S. van Hoof. Utrecht, 1993. P. 87102.*
5. B. Shaun and H. Glenn. *Microregionalism and world order: concepts, approaches and implications*. London: Palgrave Macmillan, 2003. P. 272.
6. Гулямов С.С. Моделирование социально-экономического развития территориально-промышленных комплексов. -Т.: Фан, 1980. - 194 с.;
7. Садыков А.М. Основы регионального развития: теория, методология, практика // Монография. Т.: IQTISOD - MOLIYA, 2005. - 280 с.;
8. Рузметов Б. Комплексное развитие региона в условиях углубления экономических реформ. Автореф. дис.....докт. экон. наук. –Т.: 1998;
9. Ахмедов Т.М. Регулирование территориальной организации производительных сил и комплексного развития регионов Узбекистана. -Т.: ФАН, 1992;
10. Имамов Ш.Б. Регулирование территориального развития экономики Узбекистана: Автореф. дис...докт. экон. наук. -Т.: 1998;
11. Қаюмов А.А., Назарова Х.М., Эгамбердиев Ф.Т., Якубов Ў.Ш. Минтақавий иқтисодиёт. - Т.: Университет, 2004; Назаров Ш.Х. Ўзбекистон минтақалари рақобатдошлигини оширишнинг методологик асосларини такомиллаштириш. Докторлик диссертацияси автореферати. -Т.: 2016. - 5 б.;
12. Сиддиқов А.Ж. Иқтисодий ислохотларнинг янги босқичида саноат ишлаб чиқаришнинг минтақавий муаммолари (Кашқадарё вилояти мисолида) кандидатлик диссертацияси автореферати. -Т., 2006;
13. Якубов И.О. Минтақавий иқтисодиёт. -Т.: ТДИУ, 2016.